

Hydrocarbon Potential and Structural Interpretation of the Baska Block: Insights from the Lower Ranikot and Pab Sandstone Formations in the Central Indus Basin

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the hydrocarbon potential of the Baska Block, located in the Central Indus Basin near the eastern and southeastern Sulaiman Ranges. Structural interpretation, based on time and depth contour mapping of the Lower Ranikot and Pab Sandstone formations, reveals a westward shallowing trend with multiple intersecting thrust faults. The Saviragha well closure is interpreted as a three-way fault-bounded structural trap with one dip-bounded flank. Within the Lower Ranikot Formation, two reservoir zones have been identified, exhibiting hydrocarbon saturations of 45% and 56%. The Pab Sandstone Formation comprises four reservoir zones, with hydrocarbon saturations ranging from 53% to 76%. These findings indicate significant hydrocarbon potential in both formations, highlighting the Baska Block as a promising target for future exploration and resource development.

Key words: Seismic Interpretation, Petrophysical Analysis, Lower Ranikot Formation, Pab Formation

Introduction

The research area, designated for exploration, is the Baska Block, situated in the Central Indus Basin, within the eastern and southeastern regions of the Sulaiman Ranges. The Baska North Block, encompassing an area of 2,487 square kilometers, is located within the Tank and Dera Ismail Khan districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) province. Due to its location in a region of significant compressional stress, the primary geological structures in the area are characterized by thrust faulting. The qualitative assessment of hydrocarbon resources requires combining seismic data with well data interpretations (Aizebeokhai and Olayinka, 2011). Accurate determination of reservoir characteristics is essential for the future exploration and assessment of potential oil and gas fields (Ashraf et al., 2020). Reservoir characterization includes assessing key properties such as porosity, permeability, fluid types, and the reservoir's horizontal and vertical extents, along with its boundaries (Huang et al., 2021; Iltaf et al., 2021; Toqeer et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021b). Typically, reservoir properties at

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different depths are evaluated using a combination of well logs and seismic data (Chopra and Marfurt, 2007).

Seismic techniques are widely regarded as the most effective geophysical method due to their precision, resolution, cost-efficiency, and ability to penetrate deep into the subsurface. Exploratory well sites can be determined through seismic analysis (Telford et al., 1990). Well-log data provide key insights for differentiating between shale and other formations by analyzing signals such as density, porosity, sonic transit time, and shale resistivity. Additionally, core samples, production data, and geophysical logs contribute to identifying potential hydrocarbon reservoir zones (Ali et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2021a). Combining various data sets helps reduce uncertainty when predicting rock properties, identifying subtle stratigraphic traps, and locating sweet spots within the target zone (Ali et al., 2018; Azeem et al., 2018).

This research comprises two main components with specific objectives. The first component involves interpreting 2D seismic lines from the Baska field. For this purpose, 2D seismic data was employed to delineate the major structural features of the study area. The second component of this research focuses on analyzing the petrophysical characteristics of reservoir using well log data from existing wells. The primary goal is to assess the reservoir potential by evaluating various properties such as shale volume, effective porosity and water saturation.

Regional Geological Settings

The tectonic history of the Indus Basin started with the intracratonic rifting of the Gondwanaland supercontinent during the Late Proterozoic. This was followed by a rift event in the Permian-Triassic period. During the final stages of Mesozoic rifting, the Indian Plate separated from the cratonic blocks of Afghanistan, Africa, and Seychelles, marking a significant tectonic shift. It began moving northward, leading to a significant plate convergence with the Eurasian landmass, which has continued into the Cenozoic era (Kemal et al., 1991). The oblique collision between the Indo-Pakistan Plate and the Eurasian Plate led to the anticlockwise rotation of the Indo-Pakistan Plate. This movement led to the activation of significant basement faults, including the Kirthar, Sulaiman, and Jhelum Basement Faults, which divided the Indo-Pakistan Plate into several distinct basement blocks. The ongoing collision and shifting of these blocks have produced varied tectonic patterns across the different basement blocks (Bannert and Raza, 1992).

The Sulaiman Fold and Thrust Belt (SFTB) formed as a wide, approximately 300 km broad, curved, and asymmetrical topographic feature within this geological setting (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 illustrates the regional tectonic framework of Pakistan, highlighting the Sulaiman Fold and Thrust Belt (SFTB) located at the western edge of the Indian subcontinent. The SFTB is marked by a black box (Saif ur rehman et al., 2019).

The eastern segment of the Sulaiman Fold and Thrust Belt (SFTB) exhibits a monoclinical structure, with molasse strata dipping eastward near the mountain front, positioned next to a broad syncline within the foredeep. (Humayon et al., 1991). Similarly, the southern SFTB shares this monoclinical feature, though less pronounced, with the formation of broad detachment folds, such as the Sui and Loti structures, spanning about 20 km in half-wavelength over the basement (Jadoon et al., 1992). The western and northern boundaries of the Sulaiman Fold and Thrust Belt (SFTB) are marked by the Zhob Valley Suture Zone, which consists of ophiolitic rocks that were emplaced during the time span between the Late Cretaceous and Early Eocene epochs (Jadoon and Khurshid, 1996). The rock units in the Sulaiman Fold and Thrust Belt (SFTB) are divided into three main categories: molasse deposits from the Late Oligocene to Holocene, the Late Eocene to Early Oligocene Khojak Flysch, which overlies the Zhob Valley Muslimbagh ophiolite, and sedimentary formations from the Eocene to Permian, representing environments that range from shallow to deep marine settings. (Jadoon et al., 1994a). The platform sequence ranging from the Eocene to Triassic is prominently visible in the Sulaiman Fold and Thrust Belt (SFTB). Recent updates to the regional structural and stratigraphic understanding have emphasized tectono-stratigraphic elements. (Jadoon and Zaib, 2018). In the region under study, structural models have been proposed as either thick-skinned or thin-skinned. The thick-skinned model is primarily supported by image analysis, although it relies on limited fieldwork and seismic data interpretation (Iqbal and Khan, 2012). In contrast, the thin-skinned model, advocated by regional studies that incorporate both geological and geophysical data, characterizes the Sulaiman Fold and Thrust Belt (SFTB) as a classic fold-and-thrust belt. This model indicates that the

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sedimentary layers are detached from the underlying basement and that the deformation exhibits a passive roof duplex structure (Jadoon et al., 1992, 1994a).

Data set and Methodology

The information utilized in this study was provided by the Directorate General of Petroleum Concessions (DGPC) in Pakistan. It comprises borehole log data from two wells and 2D seismic data, including four dip lines and three strike lines in SEG-Y format. The wire line logs used in the analysis include gamma ray (GR), deep resistivity (LLD), sonic (DT), caliper, density (RHOB), and spontaneous potential (SP) logs. The base map of the study area (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 The base map of research area.

SEISMIC LINE:

S.NO	SEISMIC LINE	LINE DESCRIPTION
1	BG-34-94-11	STRIKE LINE
2	BG-34-94-10	DIP LINE
3	BG-34-94-06EXT	DIP LINE
4	BG-34-94-04	DIP LINE
5	BG-34-94-03	STRIKE LINE
6	BG-34-94-02EXT	DIP LINE

SEISMIC WELL:

GULAN-01

SAVIRAGHA-01

Seismic Interpretation

The interpretation techniques mainly convert reflection data into their exact position (depths) in the seismic section, and the structural trend of the subsurface, and then correlate this interpretation with actual well data for enhancing the interpretation techniques (Atat et al. 2012). The synthetic seismogram were generated by convolving the reflectivity derived from digitized acoustic and density logs with the wavelet derived from seismic data. This synthetic seismogram was developed to confirm the horizon marked on a seismic section. Different reverse faults were marked on a seismic section and a fault polygon of that fault was generated. Time and Depth contour maps were generated and then converted time domain seismic section into depth surface maps by using velocities exact from well data.

Petrophysical Analysis

Petrophysical analysis of the well logs has always been critical for identifying and evaluating hydrocarbon-bearing zones (Kumar et al. 2018). The petrophysical analysis was performed for reservoir characterization of the Baska Block using data from the Saviragha-01 wells to calculate the quantity of shale, porosity, water, and hydrocarbon saturation. The well data for this analysis included several log curves, such as Gamma Ray (GR), Sonic Log (DT), Spontaneous Potential (SP) Log, Medium Laterolog (LL), Shallow Laterolog (LLS), Deep Laterolog (LLD), Neutron Log, Density Log (RHOB), and Photoelectric Effect (PEF), among others.

Results and Discussion

Interpreted Seismic Section

Line BG3494-06

In this section, F1, F2, F3, F4, and F5 are identified as the primary thrust sheets due to their alignment with the principal stress direction, while faults 1A, 1B, 1C, and 1D are classified as back thrusts. The well Saviragha is situated above a pop-up structure created by fault-bounded trapping mechanisms. This pop-up structure is the shallowest and thus the most advantageous location for the well site. The general westward tilting of the strata suggests the presence of a decollement zone, which is characterized in this area. The Sember formation is located within the zone between the Parh limestone and Chiltan limestone (Fig 3).

Online ISSN

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Fig. 3 Interpreted seismic Dip line BG3494-06.

Line BG3494-10

This dip line reveals three primary thrust sheets intersecting the horizons F1, F2, and F6. Five back thrusts, originating from the main thrusts F1A, F1B, F1C, F1D, and F6A, branch off from these primary thrusts. The main thrusts originate from the Sember formation, which serves as the decollement zone. In contrast, F2 directly cuts through the Sember zone and extends into the Chiltan limestone (Fig 4).

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Fig. 4 Interpreted seismic Dip line BG3494-10.

LINE BG3494-04

This dip line displays five primary thrust sheets intersecting the horizons F1, F2, F3, and F6. These thrust sheets give rise to five back thrusts: F1A, F1B, F1C, F1D, and F6A. The main thrusts originate from the Sember formation, which acts as the decollement zone. In contrast, F6, F4, and F3 originate from deeper horizons beneath the Chiltan limestone (Fig 5).

Fig. 5 Interpreted seismic Dip line BG3494-04.

Time and Depth contour map of Lower Ranikot Formation

A TWT contour map of the top Lower Ranikot Formation was created with a 0.1 millisecond interval, showing the formation cut by thrust sheets at seven points. The Saviragha well closure is a three-way fault-bounded, one-way dip-bounded trap, with the shallowest contour matching the TWT along line BG3494-06. A depth contour map, with a 100-meter interval and referenced to the Kelly Bushing, shows the shallowest depth at the well closure as 2100 meters. Both maps indicate decreasing values from east to west, suggesting the formation becomes shallower in the west (Fig. 6, 7).

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Fig. 6 Time Contour map of Lower Ranikot formation

Fig. 7 Depth contour map of Lower Ranikot Formation

Time and Depth contour map of Pab Formation

A TWT contour map of the top Pab Sandstone was generated with a 0.1 millisecond interval, showing thrust sheets cutting the formation at seven points. The Saviragha well closure is a three-way fault-bounded, one-way dip-bounded trap, with a shallowest contour value of 2.7 milliseconds, matching the TWT along line BG3494-06. The map indicates decreasing TWT values from east to west, suggesting the formation shallows westward. A depth contour map, with a 50-meter interval, shows a shallowest contour of 2650 meters at the well, with an 11-meter mistie due to well offset. Both maps confirm the westward shallowing of the formation (Fig. 8, 9).

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Fig. 8 Time Contour map of Pab formation

Fig. 9 Depth contour map of Pab Formation

Petrophysical Analysis

Interpretation results of Lower Ranikot Formation (Well Saviragha-01)

In the Lower Ranikot formation, two reservoir zones have been identified, each with the potential for hydrocarbon accumulation. These zones indicate a favorable geological environment for reservoir development, suggesting that the Lower Ranikot could be a significant target for exploration. The identification of multiple zones underscores the importance of this formation within the broader stratigraphy, offering promising opportunities for further analysis and resource extraction.

In the Saviragha-01 well, Zone-1 (2503–2524 m) has a shale volume of 18%, 13% effective porosity, 55% water saturation, and 45% hydrocarbon saturation. Zone-2 (2524–2545 m) shows 13% shale volume, 10% effective porosity, 46% water saturation, and 56% hydrocarbon saturation, indicating moderate hydrocarbon potential in both zones (Fig. 10, 11).

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Fig. 10 Zone-1 (2503 to 2524) interpretation result of Saviragha-01

Fig. 11 Zone-2 (2563 to 2580) interpretation result of Saviragha-01

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Interpretation results of Pab Formation (Well Saviragha-01)

In the Pab Sandstone Formation, four distinct reservoir zones have been identified, each exhibiting significant hydrocarbon accumulation potential. The identification of multiple reservoir zones within this formation underscores its complex geological architecture, offering promising opportunities for resource development. The Pab Formation, known for its extensive reservoir potential, is a key target for exploration due to its potential to yield substantial hydrocarbon reserves.

In the Saviragha-01 well, Zone-1 (2664–2668 m) shows a shale volume of 12%, effective porosity of 10%, water saturation of 23%, and hydrocarbon saturation of 76%. Zone-2 (2706–2710 m) exhibits 11% shale volume, 13% effective porosity, 40% water saturation, and 59% hydrocarbon saturation. Zone-3 (2728–2737 m) demonstrates 13% shale volume, 15% effective porosity, 46% water saturation, and 53% hydrocarbon saturation. Lastly, Zone-4 (2759–2763 m) presents 11% shale volume, 18% effective porosity, 41% water saturation, and 59% hydrocarbon saturation. Each zone shows strong hydrocarbon potential, as illustrated in (Fig. 12, 13, 14, 15), reinforcing the Pab Formation's significance for hydrocarbon exploration.

Fig. 12 Zone-1 (2664 to 2668) interpretation result of Saviragha-01.

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Correlation	Depth	Resistivity	Porosity Curves	Pore Space	
GR	MD	RT(LLD)	RHOB	BVW	Vshl
0	API 150	0.2 ohm.m 2000	2.000 g/cm3 3.000	0.25	0.1 1.000
SP		Ro	PHIN(NPHI)	PHIA	Yellow
-80	mV 20	0.2 2000	0.450 v/v_decima -0.150	0.25	0
CALI		Hydrocarbon	PHD(N/A)	PHE	HS
6	inches 16		0.450 -0.150	0.25	0.1 1
Sandstone			DT	Clay Water	Gas
			140.000 us/ft 40.000		
			Gas Effect	Hydrocarbon	
				Water	
				Matrix	

Fig. 13 Zone-2 (2706 to 2710) interpretation result of Saviragha-01.

Correlation	Depth	Resistivity	Porosity Curves	Pore Space	
GR	MD	RT(LLD)	RHOB	BVW	Vshl
0	API 150	0.2 ohm.m 2000	2.000 g/cm3 3.000	0.25	0.1 1.000
SP		Ro	PHIN(NPHI)	PHIA	Yellow
-80	mV 20	0.2 2000	0.450 v/v_decima -0.150	0.25	0
CALI		Hydrocarbon	PHD(N/A)	PHE	HS
6	inches 16		0.450 -0.150	0.25	0.1 1
Sandstone			DT	Clay Water	Gas
			140.000 us/ft 40.000		
			Gas Effect	Hydrocarbon	
				Water	
				Matrix	

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Fig. 14 Zone-3 (2728 to 2737) interpretation result of Saviragha-01.

Fig. 15 Zone-4 (2759 to 2763) interpretation result of Saviragha-01.

Conclusion

The evaluation of the Baska Block within the Central Indus Basin demonstrates significant hydrocarbon potential in both the Lower Ranikot and Pab Sandstone formations. Structural analysis based on TWT and depth contour mapping indicates a consistent westward shallowing trend, accompanied by multiple thrust faults that control the structural configuration of the area. The identification of two reservoir zones in the Lower Ranikot Formation and four in the Pab Sandstone Formation, characterized by favorable petrophysical properties and appreciable hydrocarbon saturation, confirms the prospectivity of the study area. Overall, these findings highlight the Baska Block as a promising target for future exploration and development, with the potential for economically viable hydrocarbon accumulations.

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